

Study of Global, National and Regional Evolution of Agritourism

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ABSTRACT

Agritourism is a relatively new phenomenon at least for India. This paper reviews the evolution of agritourism in select countries of the world, India and also at a regional level, that is, in the state of Maharashtra. With an introduction to the concept of agritourism, the article reviews evolution of agritourism in US, Australia, Europe, Italy, Sri Lanka. The evolution in India is reviewed thereafter. A focused review has been done with reference to the state of Maharashtra to gain a regional perspective. For the state of Maharashtra the article aimed at finding out if there is a disparity in the spread of agritourism. Results show that there is indeed a significant amount of disparity in the spread of agritourism within the state of Maharashtra. If there are districts having more than 100 agritourism centers, there are districts with no centers as well. This will be an interesting aspect to look into for further research.

Keywords: Agritourism, Agritourism Centers, India, Maharashtra, Regional disparity

1. INTRODUCTION

Agritourism has various definitions in various parts of the world, and some of the time alluding to farm stays and once in a while to a wide assortment of exercises, including purchasing a produce legitimately from a farm stand, navigating a corn maze, slopping pigs, picking fruit, taking care of animals, or staying at a bed and breakfast (B&B) on a farm. Definitions of agritourism are wide-going in the writing. The errors found among the different agritourism definitions identify with three issues: (1) the sort of setting (e.g., farm, any agricultural setting); (2) the credibility of the agricultural office or the experience; and (3) the types of exercises included (e.g., dwelling, training). Agritourism items and administrations can be partitioned into various types like farm convenience, farm cooking, participatory agritourism, farm retailing, therapy at the farm, holidaying in a farm and farm diversion.

It is multifaceted and may involve agricultural tourism, agro tourism, farm tourism, farm get-away tourism, wine tourism, agritourism, just as some related terms that are utilized reciprocally with agritourism or that are complementary to agritourism incorporate nature tourism, country tourism, elective farming, untamed life endeavors, ecotourism, agritainment, legacy tourism, agri instruction and worth included agriculture (Brant and Rhoades, 2007). The word reference significance of agritourism is tourism in which vacationer's board at farms or in rustic towns and experience farming at close hand (Dictionary of the English Language, 2000). Barbieri and Mshenga (2008) characterize Agritourism as "any practice developed on a working farm to draw in visitors." McGehee, Kim, and Jennings (2007) clarify agritourism as "rustic ventures which join both a working farm environment and a commercial tourism segment." Marques (2006): "a specific kind of provincial tourism where the facilitating house must be coordinated into an agricultural home, possessed by the proprietor, permitting visitors to take part in agricultural or complementary exercises on the property." Sonnino (2004) "exercises of cordiality performed by agricultural business people and their relatives that must stay associated and complementary to farming exercises." Sharpley and Sharpley (1997) "tourism items which are straightforwardly associated with the agrarian environment, agrarian items or agrarian remains." Agri tourism incorporates opening up farms to travelers from urban territories and from abroad, and letting them to take understanding of country life. Aside from enlightening them regarding the different yields and how they are planted and gathered, agri tourism opens vacationers to customary food, workmanship, culture, music and language. Travelers can get an encounter of country exercises, for example, bullock truck rides, draining dairy animals and goats and picking farm new fruits and vegetables and so forth. Advantages of agritourism are:

- It brings significant essential area agriculture closer to significant assistance part tourism. This assembly is required to make win-win circumstance for both the divisions.
- Tourism division can possibly grow.
- Agriculture division has the ability to retain development in tourism Sector.

Various activities forming part of agro-tourism:

1. A shady spot for visitors to rest – like a big banyan tree
2. Antique Villages.
3. Antiques.
4. Arts & Crafts Demonstrations.
5. Bad weather - like desert, snow fields, heavy rainfall also attract Agri-tourists
6. Bed and Breakfast
7. Cold Drinks.
8. Collection of old farm Machinery.
9. Cooking Demos to satisfy housewives.
10. Crafts Demonstrations.
11. Crafts.
12. Crop Art.
13. Cross-country skiing.
14. Demonstration of Agri-activities
15. Educational Tours for school children, officers and progressive farmers
16. Fantasyland.
17. Farm Schools to teach a particular skill
18. Farm Store : Exhibition of farm equipment
19. Farm Theme Playground for Children.
20. Farm Tours.
21. Farm Vacations.
22. Festivals with wide publicity and sponsorship
23. Food Sales.
24. Gift Shop.
25. Herb Walks.
26. Historical Recreations like highlighting a oldest farm etc.
27. Horseback Riding.
28. Log Buildings.
29. Lunch Counter.
30. Miniature Village.
31. Moonlight activities.
32. Outdoor Schools which are mobile in nature teaching agriculture
33. Pageants.
34. Pick-Your-own Pumpkin Patch.
35. Picnic Grounds.
36. Pizza Farm.
37. Processing of farm products and sale
38. Regional Themes like tribal coffee of Kerala, Andaman spices etc
39. Rent –an – apple tree.

40. Restaurant.
41. Roadside Stand selling fresh farm products and craft items
42. Speakers who can attract Agro-tourist narrating Agricultural experiences.
43. Theme (apple town, etc.)
44. Wool Processing.
45. Workshops on interesting, emerging agriculture topics

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The activity of agritourism has been proposed as a feasible choice for on-farm broadening (Amanor-Boadu, 2013; Bagi and Reeder, 2012; Galinato et al., 2010; Joo et al., 2013). Amanor-Boadu (2013) analyzed agritourism related exercises as methods for broadening and found that financial and training factors are decidedly spurring factors in such exercises, notwithstanding the impact of socioeconomics. Joo et al. (2013) found that little farms taking an interest in agritourism created a more noteworthy family unit salary than bigger farms. Be that as it may, some farm explicit qualities, for example, administrator's farming experience, access to capital, and the size of the farm activity assume a noteworthy job in deciding a farm's cooperation in agritourism. There are various examinations that engaged to a great extent on buyer inspirations, request, and guest attributes, interest for agritourism goals, and more extensive rural points of view (for example Che et al., 2007; Jensen et al., 2006, 2014; McGehee et al., 2007; Nickerson et al., 2001). Writing underpins that urban individuals will in general visit agritourism farms and take dynamic part in the great exercises (Che et al., 2005; McGehee, 2007; Wilson et al., 2006) yet how (and whether) the urban status of an area influences agritourism despite everything should be researched and liable to be put in a particular setting. Illbery (1991) found that closeness to a significant urban market influenced the broadening choice on the urban edge of the UK's West Midlands.

A comparable pattern was seen in New Jersey. Schilling and Sullivan (2014) recognized that farms closer to the urban focus of New York City were altogether bound to offer agritourism attractions than farms further away from the urban center. Joo et al. (2013), for instance, utilizing across the country huge US information, found that the probability of farms taking an interest in agritourism exercises expanded as they are further from a urban focus. Studies recommend that nearness to buyer showcases, the structure and synthesis of purchaser markets (pay, populace thickness and development), transportation, and the regular comforts/recreational scores of an area could assume a key job in the affinity to begin an agritourism activity. Another factor – salary – has regularly been portrayed as a significant factor in open air diversion investment. Examination on outside entertainment regularly refers to salary as one of the most significant indicators of support (Alexandris and Carroll, 1997; Brown et al., 2001; Kelly, 1980; Lee et al., 2001; Scott and Munson, 1994; Searle and Jackson, 1985; Shores et al., 2007; White, 1975). Joo et al. (2013) found that higher family unit pay in a region and the quantity of agritourism farm working in the region has an altogether positive relationship in the US.

3. METHODS

Research Gap

There is no study that takes a global, national and a regional perspective. This study looks at all the three levels together.

Following methodology was designed for the study -

- a. Discuss the global evolution with reference to select destinations - US, Australia, Europe, Italy, Sri Lanka
- b. Discuss Indian evolution
- c. Carry an analysis of agri-tourism centers in Maharashtra
- d. Analyze their spread.

4. GLOBAL EVOLUTION OF AGRITOURISM

Agritourism in United States

Agritourism is recognized by various names in various parts of the world. Agrotourism, farm tourism, Agritourism, agricultural tourism, agri-tainment are a portion of the other option and related terms with Agritourism. To think about the earlier and start of Agritourism history, writing takes us to America where in the late nineteenth century urban families used to visit relative's farm in the late spring season to appreciate occasions and to escape from summer heat in populated region. As the transportation mode simple via car innovation and improvement, provincial visits were famous among the urban territory in second decade of nineteenth century. After the extraordinary worldwide gloom in 1929 and World War II wide open visit and entertainment turned into an approach to escape from pressure. In 1960-1980 urban people were keen on riding ponies, petting farm animals, encountering provincial life which prompted beginning of commercial farm visits, farm

settlement and farm overnight boardinghouse. As the urbanization just as hole between non-farm families and farmers surpasses, farm get-away business demonstrated surprising increment and right from 1990s, Agritourism turned into a urgent business for farmers of America which had an extraordinary monetary effect on them and encompassing networks.

Laurie S. Z. Greenberg (2006) noted about Agritourism business in U.S., —Nature tourism and Agritourism are the two quickest developing fragments of the tourism showcase in the U.S., with 30% development expected in the period 1997-2007.

As indicated by the review of Federal Reserve Board in Kansas, tourism is getting progressively critical to the U.S. economy where fundamental travel and tourism industry represented 3.6 % of all work. Besides, one out of each 18 people in U. S. has work straightforwardly coming about because of movement uses.

HyungsukChoo (2012) and Ilsson PA (2002) noticed that generally speaking, country tourism, where Agritourism is a subset, encountered a yearly development pace of 6% in North America just as Europe from 2002 to 2004. As per one across the nation study directed by Barry JJ, Hellerstain D. in 2004, 62 million Americans visited farms at least multiple times in 2000, which relates to practically 30% of the populace.

As referenced above, in America farmers having Agritourism business offer different exercises to the agritourists like U-pick activities (fruits and vegetables), riding ponies, farm represents new farm items just as for provincial items like hand creates, nearby learning and tasting of cheddar making or wine making and so forth.

In America, state astute Agritourism places are set up by strategy creators and farmers to get the most extreme monetary advantages by changing over ordinary farm into the commercial tourism farm. Farm focus at California University has developed database pretty much all current Agritourism places all through the California state. They demonstrated that Agritourism is one best option for improving wages and monetary practicality of little farms and provincial communities(George, H.,Getz, C.,&Hardesty,S., 2011).

Another relationship in North Carolina named Handmade' in America is utilizing Agritourism to build up the neighborhood economy and art exchanges, and to instruct travelers about agriculture practices.

They have clarified in regards to Agritourism on their site that —Agritourism is a specialty showcase that not just helps networks with answers for help expand their monetary base, yet it additionally helps our local urban focuses and progressively rural populaces to comprehend the significant job that farming and rustic life plays in our history, by featuring the requirement for it in our contemporary society. Agritourism ventures fortify the need to help neighborhood cultivators and sources and permit the guest to encounter what it is to be a piece of the land.

Numerous books have been distributed in America advancing Agritourism which unmistakably mirrors the Agritourism improvement in America. The distribution, Promoting Tourism in Rural America gathered by Liam R. Kennedy Clarion University of Pennsylvania clarifies the requirement for planning and showcasing country network and gauging the upsides and downsides of tourism. As per this book, —local resident interest is useful and ought to be remembered for beginning any sort of a tourism program which additionally improves the network.

Agritourism expert Jane Eckert advancing Agritourism through site, provincial abundance got this business more clarity of mind. Her blog profiles farm stays and tracks Agritourism news.

Agritourism in Australia

From most recent two decades Agritourism in Australia is additionally spreading its wings over the entire nation. Agritourism business in Australia demands to fabricate socially, environmentally, and financially stable tourism organizations. Agritourism offers their country networks the chance of broadening tourism into provincial regions in a practical manner. Best of all, relationship in Australia are turning out to be media in the middle of country travelers and farmers and developing their farm-based endeavors. They have exceptionally featured the neighborliness nature of farmers with explanation, —There's in no way like the inviting grin of an Aussie farmer. The site Agritourism Australia 'depicts advancement of Agritourism business in Australia.

Agritourism in Europe

In numerous European country networks, tourism has become amazing motor of financial development. Dan Bernardo, Luc Valentin, and John Leatherman (2004) referenced that —Agritourism and different types of on-farm expansion have

developed into an expanding prerequisite for monetary solidness in farm organizations across Western Europe. Around 33% of all farm organizations in the United Kingdom are presently occupied with nontraditional agricultural ventures, and farmer association in Agritourism in France and Italy is even higher.

Belinda Xarba, Hidajet Shehu (2011) noted significance of Agritourism improvement in European nations. Expressing the need of Agritourism they call attention to that —Structural changes in economies are causing serious worry in numerous country zones particularly for those with a high reliance on agriculture. Thus, all the concerned specialists including strategy creators and nearby pioneers were looking for finding inventive routes so as to determine the monetary issues of these regions. The European Union developed a system to help rustic incorporated improvement to determine the issues of the provincial regions in which Agritourism possesses a significant position.

Agritourism in Italy

In Italy in the time of 1970, little scope farming turned out to be less beneficial; numerous farmers move to enormous towns in the hunt of employment. In the year 1985 Italian Govt. made the law and propelled the idea of Agritourism which really is a farm house accessible for vacationers to appreciate the rustic life in Italy and in invert for farmers it is the best approach to expand the farm pay. These focuses are absolutely country in nature and give rural experience to the explorers. A portion of the focuses are large and sumptuous which give world class offices to the vacationers thus these Agritourism are effective in drawing in residential just as outside travelers in Italy. These focuses demand to serve the food to the travelers that are set up from their own farm produce or possibly locally accessible.

Agro-tourism in Sri Lanka

As substantiated by Dr. S.M.P Senanayke, Rev. Dr. Wijitapure Wimalaratana (2005) and S.H. P. Malkanthi and j. K. Routry (2011) Agritourism segment of Sri Lanka is still in its underlying stages. Sri Lanka is an agricultural nation and it has additionally assorted agro-climatic conditions appropriate for developing various types of harvests, fruits, vegetables and trees. Not many agro-tourism goals are working at present with general offices and services. The amazing increment in the enthusiasm encompassing the idea of agro-tourism of different nations is affecting the advancement of Agritourism in Sri Lanka.

Above scientists have centered specialities of Sri Lanka's Agritourism as, —complex paddy development frameworks with history of 2500 years, culling tea leaves utilizing the conventional bag-on-the-back' strategy, elastic tapping under master direction, gigantic and exceptionally old water system tanks, numerous tea and elastic plantations, draining steers on dairy farms, or in any event, working in numerous picturesque paddy fields (furrowing utilizing bullocks, chip away at paddy nurseries, transplanting seedlings in sloppy fields). Their examination results uncovered that there are a few opportunities for the foundation of Agritourism in the Sri Lanka.

5. EVOLUTION OF AGRITOURISM IN INDIA

Development of Tourism as an Industry in India

Relaxation travel was related with the Industrial Revolution in the United Kingdom. It allowed a chance to new white collar class developing because of mechanical transformation to go for recreation. The primary authority travel organization 'Cox and Kings' was set up in the year 1758. Tourism was distinguished as an income creating part in western nations. In India the situation was entirely unexpected. Since her freedom in 1947, Indian approach creators had generally dismissed tourism industry as it was viewed as an extravagance portion profiting just few. As at that point, the Indian economy relied a ton upon agriculture, the administration arrangements had consistently meant to create agriculture and other united regions. Tourism was constantly seen as an industry serving the first class as opposed to being acknowledged as a way to furnish work with great "multiplier impact". In 1955, the primary Planning Commission of India had set tourism industry 269th in its need list. Subsequently in 1950's the quantity of International voyagers visiting India was simply around 15000. Tourism was considered as a simple method to address remote trade lack. Thusly lodgings, food and drink, crafted works and numerous different services in the vast majority of the vacationer goals in India had customarily been overrated. Despite the fact that in 2000, Global tourism industry spoke to perhaps the biggest business in the world with income of \$595 billion and the quantity of visitor appearances comprehensively as high as 698 million; India's offer in worldwide tourism stayed low.

Because of boosting country improvement from tourism perspective and support of tourism infrastructure advancement in provincial zones by state governments, Agri-Tourism Development Corporation was built up on sixteenth May 2004 in Maharashtra. "Its point is to elevate Agro Tourism to assist provincial youth with earning great good living in the town and

on the farm itself. First historically speaking International Agri-Tourism day was commended on sixteenth May, 2008 in Pune. The 'Tenth Five Year Plan' opened up following open doors for agritourism in India.

Agritourism Opportunities in India

- Indian tourism industry is developing @10.1%. The World Tourism association has evaluated that the tourism business is developing at the pace of 4% per year and that constantly 2010 there will be more than one billion sightseers visit different parts of the world. In any case, Indian tourism industry is developing at the pace of 10% which is 2½ times more than the development rate at worldwide level. By presenting Agro-tourism idea, present development rate is continued as well as this worth expansion adds to assist development.
- India has entered among the best 10 vacationer goals list India is now settled as one of the top vacationer goal in the world. Worth expansion by presenting novel items like Agro-tourism would just fortify the intensity of Indian tourism industry in worldwide market.
 India has various culture and topography which give sufficient and boundless extension to the development of this business. India has different agro-climatic conditions, various yields, people, culture, deserts, mountains, seaside frameworks and islands which give extension to promotion all things considered, multi-area tourism items.
- Expanding number of travelers leaning toward non-urban places of interest. Consequently, there is degree for promotion of non-urban places of interest in inside towns by setting up Agro-tourism focuses. In any case, sufficient offices and exposure are must to advance such focuses.
- Government activities and approaches in X five-year allocation have been expanded from 525 crores to 2900 crores. Expanded monetary allocation reaffirms the administration responsibility. The expanded budgetary allocation by multiple times could be utilized for capacity building of service providers, making of infrastructure and exposure.

Agritourismcenters in Maharashtra

Following is the district-wise spread of agritourismcenters in Maharashtra as per www.agritourism.in/ –

Sr .No.	District	ATC's
1	Ahmednagar	13
2	Akola	0
3	Amravati	4
4	Aurangabad	4
5	Beed	2
6	Bhandara	0
7	Buldhana	0
8	Chandrapur	4
9	Dhule	2
10	Gadchiroli	0
11	Gondia	0
12	Hingoli	0
13	Jalgaon	2
14	Jalna	1
15	Kolhapur	11
16	Latur	1
17	Mumbai	0
18	Nagpur	7
19	Nanded	1
20	Nandurbar	1
21	Nashik	12
22	Osmanabad	1
23	Palghar	2

24	Parbhani	1
25	Pune	107
26	Raigad	29
27	Ratnagiri	10
28	Sangli	3
29	Satara	88
30	Sindhudurg	2
31	Solapur	8
32	Thane	22
33	Wardha	3
34	Washim	1
35	Yavatmal	0
	Total	342
(Source: http://www.agritourism.in/)		

6. RESULTS

Descriptive statistics for the 35 ATC's is as under –	
Statistic	ATC's
Number of observations	35
Minimum	0.000
Maximum	107.000
Range	107.000
Variance (n)	511.891
Variance (n-1)	526.946
Standard deviation (n)	22.625
Standard deviation (n-1)	22.955
Skewness (Pearson)	3.432
Kurtosis (Pearson)	10.861
Standard error of the mean	3.880

The spread of the Agritouristcenters in Maharashtra over the 35 districts is quite uneven as indicated by high values of standard deviation, variance etc. While Pune has 107 ATC's there are districts like Akola that do not have a single ATC.

CONCLUSION

Agritourism is steadily developing into an industry. It has good prospects given the rapid pace of urbanization. People from the urban areas would like to visit agritourist spots for relaxation and vacations. The concept is well-spread across the world with its development seen in countries from US to Sri Lanka. In India the Xth 5-year plan gave recognition to agritourism and measures have been taken to promote the concept in the country. State of Maharashtra has shown good progress with more than 300 agritourist centers spread across 35 districts. However the spread is not uniform and shows high disparity. Districts that are lagging behind should be brought at par with others.

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